

THE ROLE OF COMMUNITY DYNAMICS IN KIDNAPPING AND DEPRESSION IN CHIKUN, KADUNA STATE

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Abstract:

The study investigated the alleged community stimulus of kidnapping on depression in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State. Survey research design was adopted with accidental sampling technique. Two hundred and thirty-two (232) participated in the study both male and female. A standardized instrument was used to collect data which is Patient Health Questionnaire 9 (PQH-9). The data were further analyzed using Chi-Square, One-Way ANOVA and Independent Sample-t-test. Hypothesis one revealed that, there is a significant difference in the perceived association of news on kidnapping and depression in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State, $X^2(1) = 37.274, P < 0.05$. In other words, the hypothesis was confirmed in this study. Hypothesis two tested a significant difference in gender and depression in Chikun LGA. Analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between male and female participants in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State, $t(230) = -5.110, P < 0.05$. In other words, the stated hypothesis was confirmed in this study. We therefore, concluded and recommended that, even though residents are aware of such activities, the level of PTSD experienced by them has been relatively low but relatively high depression. Family and community ties and togetherness should be strengthened since it promotes resilience which in turn act as a buffer or immune to developing PTSD or depression.

Keywords: *community stimulus, kidnapping, depression and posttraumatic stress disorder.*

INTRODUCTION

The primary responsibility of any government is the protection of lives and properties but the desired levels of security in Nigeria have been a mirage especially since the onset of the year 2007. Security is any mechanism deliberately fashioned to alleviate the most serious and immediate threats that prevent people from pursuing their values (Abamara & Dike, 2018). Where security is lacking, it become a threat not only to the government but citizens as well. Lack of security of any form affects economic activities and also results to loss of numerous lives, psychological trauma, and internal displacement etc. The highest peak of insecurity is made visible through the process of holding someone against his wish and turning him/her into a property for bargaining is a phenomenon called kidnapping (Ungar, 2011).

Depression is a common and serious medical illness that negatively affects how you feel the way you think and how

you act. Fortunately, it is also treatable. Depression causes feelings of sadness and/or a loss of interest in activities once enjoyed. It can lead to a variety of emotional and physical problems and can decrease a person's ability to function at work and at home. Depression symptoms can vary from mild to severe

and can include: Feeling sad or having a depressed mood, Loss of interest or pleasure in activities once enjoyed, Changes in appetite leading to weight loss or gain unrelated to dieting, Trouble sleeping or sleeping too much, Loss of energy or increased fatigue, Increase in purposeless physical activity or slowed movements and speech, Feeling worthless or guilty, Difficulty thinking, concentrating or making decisions and thoughts of death or suicide (Ranna, 2017).

It is equally a state of low mood and aversion to activities. It can affect a person's thoughts, behaviour, motivation, feelings, and sense of well-being. It may feature sadness, difficulty in thinking and concentration and a significant increase or decrease in appetite and time spent sleeping. People experiencing depression may have feelings of dejection, hopelessness and, sometimes, suicidal thoughts. It can either be short term or long term (de Zwart, Jeronimus & de Jonge, 2019). The core symptom of depression is said to be anhedonia, which refers to loss of interest or a loss of feeling of pleasure in certain activities that usually bring joy to people.

Okafor, Ajibo, Chukwu, Egbuche and Asadu (2018) in a study on kidnapping and hostage-taking in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria and the implication for social work intervention with victims, found that kidnapped victims in Niger Delta region of Nigeria go through a lot of psycho-social trauma and shock. Physical pains are being inflicted on victims by the abductors in most cases. Victims are depressed and they more often than not develop psychological problem if intervention is not brought to bear quickly. Both the victim and the family of the victim are financially stressed out because of the huge amount of money which runs in millions that are usually demanded by abductors. According to Bailey (2018) traumatic experiences leave an everlasting impact on an individual. Disastrous situations can change an individual, and mould them into a whole new person. A devastating event such as kidnapping impact on the individual in many ways. The behaviour of a kidnapped victim differs greatly before and after the trauma. With the kidnapping there are many obstacles, and after the release there are even more difficulties to be faced. How an individual [victim] handles those effects and challenges all depends on their mind and effort to overcome them. Kidnappings have many effects on victims including: compromising their ability to trust, undermining their ability to feel safe, and causing the suffering they face with Stockholm syndrome.

Thabet, Thabet and Panos, (2016), conducted a study on the relationship between War Trauma, PTSD, Depression, and Anxiety among 250 Palestinian children in the Gaza Strip. The study found that Palestinian children reported symptoms of depression. The minimum symptoms were 0 and maximum were 36 with mean depression 18.38 (SD=6.48). Considering the cut-off point of CDI of 19 and above for depression, 127 children (50.6%) were depressed. In order to find the differences in depression and sex, an independent t test was performed. The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences between boys and girls in depression. There were no age differences in reported depression. The results showed that the most common traumatic events due to war reported by children were hearing shelling of the area by artillery, hearing the sonic sounds of jetfighters, watching mutilated bodies on TV, and hearing shootings and bombardment. Mean Impact of Events Scale was 18.37, intrusion subscale mean was 8.98, avoidance subscale mean was 9.49, 148 children were in the clinical range for post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms (59%). Study showed that 21.9% of children had anxiety and 50.6% had depression. Total traumatic events were significantly correlated PTSD, avoidance, arousal symptoms, anxiety, and depression.

Kerig, Ward, Vanderzee, and Arnzen Moeddel (2009) found that PTSD mediated the relationship between trauma exposure and mental health problems in a sample of incarcerated adolescents; in this

study the effects were stronger for girls than boys. Among those that have looked separately at PTSD symptom clusters, patterns of gender differences also have emerged. Allwood and Bell (2008) found that, for a community sample of girls exposed to violence, symptoms of re-experiencing were related to self-reported aggression against others, whereas for boy's symptoms of arousal mediated the relationship between exposure to and perpetration of violence. In turn, avoidance of trauma reminders was negatively related to the perpetration of violence, suggesting that efforts to turn mental attention away from the traumatic event might be protective against the tendency to re-enact it against others. A different pattern of gender differences emerged in a study of incarcerated delinquent youth by Kerig, Ward, Vanderzee, and Arnzen Moeddel, (2009) who found that, for boys but not girls, PTSD symptoms of re-experiencing and arousal were related to anger/irritability.

Security is referred to as any mechanism deliberately fashioned to alleviate the most serious and immediate threats, that prevent people from pursuing their values. According to Zannoni (2003), Kidnapping for ransom is a varied and developing phenomenon, but it is most common in countries with high levels of crime and corruption, poorly resourced or trained police personnel, a weak judiciary, and/or a history of political or social instability and Nigeria was ranked a coming after Mexico, Brazil, Colombia, Venezuela and Philippines (Clayton, 2004) but by 2012, she has emerged as the 4th of the Top Ten Kidnap for Ransom nations in the world (Akhigbe & Keleoso, 2013). Zannoni (2003) says motivations and modus operandi behind every kidnap vary, but generally there are two main kinds of kidnapping for ransom. These can be roughly categorized as "criminal kidnapping", where the main motive is to obtain a ransom from the family or business of the victim. This category includes instances where criminals take hostages as a shield to help them escape from the scene of a crime, or use them to obtain money or valuables, or the keys or secret codes needed to access areas where these are stored. Ralph (2008) described a type of kidnapping, very similar to the cases in Nigeria, which he refers to as "tiger kidnapping". It involves the abduction or holding of a hostage with the intention of forcing an employee or his/her relative to facilitate the immediate theft of valuables or to concede some other form of ransom from an institution or business organization. In this type of kidnapping, it is not necessarily the executives that are at risk, but those at middle and lower management positions targeted as victims or accomplices. The other type of kidnapping, according to Zannoni (2003) is "political kidnapping", where the foremost objective is to further the political aims of a particular political group or movement. In this case, a ransom is usually demanded to obtain money for the group to fund their activities. For whichever type of kidnapping, the psychological and financial impact can be quite devastating, both for the victims and their significant others.

Statement of Research Problem

Kidnapping is a rising worldwide widespread activities with no truthful resolution to the menace. Numerous reasons have remained branded as being associated with kidnapping. Some of these comprises communal and moral corruption, encouragement of peer group, culture of drug abuse, mass media, ethnic nationalism, ethnic militia, god-fatherism and elites, economy, population, family influence, among others (Shekwolo, Newton, Sunday & Fenan, 2020). Kidnapping has become a national problem that no nation, state or local government is free of and is seen as a global menace. Kaduna state has become a bee hive of kidnapping with several cases recorded in Chikun Local Government area of Kaduna state. Studies on kidnapping had been conducted in Nigeria and even in Kaduna state but neglecting Chikun local government.

The understudy Local Government is situated in Kaduna State and one of the places in Northern Nigeria with continued and persistent cases of kidnapping activities. In August 2019, a pregnant woman and two minors were kidnapped in a community called Juji; on the 16th September 2019 in the same local government, a pastor, his daughter and a church treasurer were kidnapped in another community Kankomi and in the same month a business man and his three sons were kidnapped in Sabon Tasha. On the 3rd October 2019, six female students and two teachers of Engravers College in Kakau Daji were kidnapped with ransom paid before they were released. On the 9th and 25th January 2020, four Seminarians from the Good Shepherd Major Seminary in Kakau Kaduna and a house wife in Juji with her two children were kidnapped respectively. On the 1st February, 2020 a KADGIS worker was kidnapped at Mararaban-Rido; all these in Chikun Local Government (Ezeobi, Ehigiator & Ozulumba, 2020). These are the few cases of kidnapping among others that happened in Chikun local government area of Kaduna state. The high incidence of kidnapping today in our society may be attributed to insecurity both in the home, at schools, market places, parks, high ways etc. One would imagine that being kidnapped is an exceptionally high-intensity traumatic event, inducing feelings of helplessness, horror, and fear for one's life. Victims typically take many years to heal from the psychological wounds inflicted upon them, and some never completely recover. Several studies have been conducted on causes and consequences of kidnapping among victims and even among loved ones but non on the alleged community stimulus of kidnapping on Depression in Chikun Local Government area of Kaduna state.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the alleged community stimulus of kidnapping on depression in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State More specifically the study intends to:

- i. Examine the relationship between kidnapping and Depression in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna state.
- ii. To examine gender differences in Post- Traumatic Stress Disorder and Depression among the populace in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna state.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between kidnapping and Depression in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna state?
- ii. What is the gender differences in Post- Traumatic Stress Disorder and Depression among the populace in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna state?
- iii.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The study adopted survey research design using accidental sampling technique. This was found suitable for the study because it permits the researcher to gather information without manipulating the variables and the data required is reasonably precise and conversant to the participants and the researcher has substantial prior information of the glitches understudy.

Participants

The participants in this study were two hundred and thirty- two (232) adult males and females, residing in various settlements in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. Demographic characteristics of 232 participants (male = 116 and female = 116). Age: 18-23 years (N=78, 53.6%), 24-29 years (N=66, 28.4%), 30-35 years

(N=57, 24.6%) and 36 years above (N= 31, 13.4%). Marital status: single (N= 129, 55.6%), married (N= 72, 31%), widow (N= 13, 5.6%), widower (N= 12, 5.2%) and divorced (N= 6, 2.6%). Education: primary (N= 26, 11.2%) secondary (N= 101, 43.5%) and tertiary (N= 105, 45.3%). Occupation: business (N= 106, 45.7%), civil servant (N= 46, 19.8%), farming (N= 35, 15.1%) and others (N= 45, 19.4%).

Instruments

Patient Health Questionnaire - 9 (PQH-9) was used as instrument to collect data in the area where Kidnapping activities has been rampant. The Patient Health Questionnaire 9 was developed by Kurk, Robert and Janet (1999). The PHQ- 9 is a screening instrument for measuring the presence of depression. It is 9 items with responses on a four scales of 'Not at all'; 'Several days' 'More than half the days' and 'Nearly every day'. According to Adewuya, Ola, and Afolabi (2006) the PHQ-9 has a good psychometric property among Nigerian population. Because of its validity, reliability, brevity and ease of administration, the PHQ-9 is a valuable tool for estimating depression among Nigeria population. It has been used and validated among Nigerian population. It has an internal reliability and a good concurrent validity with the Beck Depression Inventory ($r=0.67$, $P<0.001$). It also has a good $r=0.84$ and one-month test-retest reliability (Adewuya et al 2006).

Procedure

The Researcher used the scientific method which is essentially following the step by step process that a researcher can follow to determine if there is some type of relationship between two or more variables. The process involves the identification of Chikun Local Government Area as the research area because of the high prevalence of kidnapping in the area, non-existence of prior research on the subject matter of this research and the enthusiasm of the researcher on kidnapped victim's mental health. Data was collected using self-administered questionnaires. This research requires primary data, that is, direct responses from participants. The researcher in company of a colleague (research assistant) on the said day of data collection went to Juji a settlement in Sabo where kidnapping activities have been on the increase in recent months. While there, the researcher walked around and administered the instruments to adults who are available. Their consent was however sought before they were given the questionnaires to fill.

Statistical Technique Used

The data collected using questionnaires was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). While the demographic variables were analysed using frequency and percentages. The data were further analysed using inferential statistics for the test of Hypotheses. Chi-Square test was used to test the perceived association between kidnapping and depression level in Chikun, Kaduna. One-Way ANOVA and Independent Sample-t-test was used to test for mean difference. Finally, the results were presented in tables for easy comprehension. **Ethical Considerations**

As required of any psychological research, ethics considered and used in this study include the following:

Participants were briefed on the nature and purpose of the study prior to administering the questionnaire. Participants consents to participate in the study were sought before there were administered with the questionnaire after which were informed that they were free to discontinue from participating in the study at any time or stage they so desire to. Finally, participants were informed that the study was meant for educational purpose only, hence their response were kept confidential and

used only for the purpose it was meant for. They were asked not to include their names or phone numbers.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: Hypothesis one stated that, there will be a significant relationship between kidnapping and depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. This hypothesis was test using Chi-Square test in table

1

Table 1: Perceived Association between Kidnapping and Depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State

Depression		NS	MS	TOTAL	χ^2	SIG.
VARIABLES		F(%)	F(%)	F(%)		
Heard of Kidnapping						
YES	51(22)	109(47)	160(69)			
NO	54(23.3)	18(7.8)	72(31)	37.274	0.000	
Total	105(45.3)	127(54.7)	232(100)			

Sig. Level: $P < .05$, $df=1$

Table 1 shows the summary of Chi-Square test of the perceived association of kidnapping and depression. The result revealed that 160(69%) of the participants have heard of kidnapping, of which 109(47%) indicate high level of depression and 51(22%) indicate low level of depression. Also, the result reveal that 72(31%) of the participants have not heard of kidnapping, of which 54(23.3%) indicate low level of depression and 18(7.8%) indicate high level of depression. Generally, the result revealed that 54.7% were highly depressed while 45.3% were less depressed. Further analysis revealed that there is a significant difference in the perceived association of news on kidnapping and depression $X^2(1) = 37.274$, $P < 0.05$ in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State. In other words, the hypothesis was confirmed in this study.

Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis two stated that, there will be a significant difference in gender and depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. This hypothesis was tested using Independent Sample t-test in table 2.

Table 2: Summary Results of the Difference between Male and Female Perceived Depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State.

Gender	N	M	SD	df	t	P
Male	116	12.33	5.897			
Female	116	15.91	4.700			

$t(230) = -5.110$, $P < 0.05$

Table 2 shows the summary results of the independent sample t-test analysis where the mean and standard deviation scores of males ($M= 12.33$; $SD= 5.897$) and females ($M= 15.91$; $SD= 4.700$). Furthermore, the analysis revealed a statistically significant, $t(230)= -5.110$, $P < 0.05$ difference between male and female participants in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. In other words, the stated hypothesis was confirmed in this study.

DISCUSSION

The main purpose of this study was to examine perceived perceptions of kidnapping as well as its influence on Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder and Depression among selected residents in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. The researcher made use of survey research design with the aid of self-administered questionnaires to collect responses of participants regarding the subject matter. In the course of the study, four hypotheses were generated in line with the objectives of the study. The result outcomes are discussed in relation to the hypotheses earlier generated.

The first hypothesis states that “There will be a significant relationship between kidnapping and depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna state.” While this hypothesis was tested using Chi-Square, findings from the test of hypothesis showed that there was a significant relationship between kidnapping and depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. This result finding is supported by findings of Okafor, Ajibo, Chukwu, Egbuche and Asadu (2018) who in their study on kidnapping and hostage-taking in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria found that kidnapped victims as well as family members experience heightened depression and anxiety due to the horrific treatment in the hands of the kidnappers as well as having live with the reality that loved ones were kidnapped as well as having to source for money to pay for ransom by family members. Similarly, study of Bailey (2018) on depression experienced as a result of kidnapping activities traumatic also supports the findings from the present study as people both victims and their family members experience depression due to the perceived actions of kidnapping activities in their communities.

A major reason for people having to experience depression due to kidnapping activities could be as result of horrible experiences and information they may have heard as shared by victims who were abducted and later released. More so, depression may increase as a result of the perceived fear, worry and anxiety on where and how to get money to pay for ransom in the event on kidnapping. News about kidnapping no doubt leave a lasting negative impression on some individuals which in turn may expose them to depression.

The second hypothesis states that, “There will be a significant difference in gender and Depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna state.” Test of this hypothesis was carried out using Independent Sample T-test and the outcome showed there was a significant difference in gender and depression in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. The outcome of this analysis supports the findings of Kerig, Ward, Vanderzee, and Arnzen Moeddel (2009) who found significant gender difference in participants’ responses to depression.

They concluded in their study that males experience lesser depression when compared to their female counterparts. The present finding is also supported by the findings of Allwood and Bell (2008) who reported a significant gender differences in terms of being exposed to depression in their study.

No doubt males and females respond differently to different situations especially on that has to do with kidnapping. For the reason that females tend to more sensitive and emotional than their male counterparts, they are more likely to respond to kidnapping and depression compared to males who may worry less and tend to overcome depression related emotions.

CONCLUSION

This study examines alleged community stimulus of kidnapping and its influence on Depression among residents in Chikun Local Government of Kaduna State. Survey research design using questionnaire was used to carry out the study. Findings show that participants are aware of the activities of increased kidnapping activities going on in their localities which has created a lasting negative impression on them. Findings revealed that even though residents are aware of such activities, the level of depression experienced by them has been relatively high depression. It further revealed that gender (male or female) of residents do influence depression positively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the present study, below are the recommendations made by the researcher:

I. Family and community ties and togetherness should be strengthened since it promotes resilience which in turn act as a buffer or immune to developing depression. With resilience factors in the environment such the family and community support, people are more likely to overcome or cope in times of adversity and kidnapping in particularly rather than developing mental issues.

II. Children whether males or females should be raised in similar way such that females like their male counterparts can stand the test of time even in the midst of adversity rather than developing symptoms of depression in any little adverse situation.

III. People should talk to others or seek help from professionals like psychologists whenever they experience less or mild symptoms of psychological health issues rather than remaining in silence from where they might end up having depression or other anxiety related disorders.

Implication of Findings

These findings have several implications for both the public, the mental health professionals and the research community.

To the general public, the findings is a confirmation that people are most likely to develop psychological problems such as depression as result of kidnapping and other adverse activities going in the environment.

However, with a strong family or community support as well as psychological services provided on time, they are likely to cope, adapt or overcome such psychological health problems.

To the mental health professionals such as psychiatrists and psychologists, the findings is pointer to the many cause of psychological health problem, hence it will help them properly design an appropriate treatment plan taking into considerations the prevailing circumstances in which the patients found themselves.

To the research community, the findings from this study will add to the existing body of knowledge as well as open or provoke further enquiry to research especially on the reason(s) why there is relatively low depression symptoms in participants who experienced kidnapping activities in their locality.

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